

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17548251

Effect Of Entrepreneurship Education On Acquisition Of Employable Skills And Competencies Among Business Education Students Of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto

Abdulkadir Aminu Ladan¹; ²Umar Abubakar Sokoto PhD (SK) & ³Amina Isah Wasagu

¹State College of Basic and Remedial Studies, Sokoto, Nigeria

Email:abdulkadiraminuladan@gmail.com

Phone No.+2348033320469

^{2,3}Department of Business Education

Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto, Nigeria

²Email:humairaskumar2013@gmail.com/ Phone No. +2349035967384

³Email: aminahwasagu4@gmail.com/ Phone No.+2348036201208

ABSTRACT

The study examined the effect of entrepreneurship education on acquisition of employable skills and competencies among business education students in Usmanu Danfodiyo, University Sokoto. It was premised as two research objectives and corresponding two research questions, employing a survey research design approach. The target population comprised 300 students and 30 lecturers of the University with 45 participants selected through a simple random sampling technique Data collection was carried out via a structured Likert scale questionnaire, measuring responses on a continuum from Strong Agreement to Strong Disagreement measuring Strong remind. Descriptive statistics was used for analysis. The findings indicated there Disagreement. Entrepreneurship education as significant effect on acquisition of employable skills and competencies among students. Based on the results of the findings, it was recommended that students should be encouraged by entrepreneurship education teachers or lecturers to put into practice the knowledge acquired during their studentship in order to be self-reliant and that sheets should pursue further training and acquisition of skills even after graduation from University, college to further develop their skills and competencies

Keywords: Entrepreneurship Education, Acquisition of Employable skills and competencies, Usmanu Danfodiyo University of Education Students.

INTRODUCTION

It is common knowledge that Nigeria's labor market is characterized by unprecedented unemployment in the present times. The National Bureau of Statistics (NBS. 2024) indicated that about 20 million Nigerian youth of productive age, are either unemployed or underemployed and about 133 million Nigerians are plunged into multidimensional poverty as a result of this menace. In the past after graduating from tertiary institutions, people did not have to wait for long period of time before finding their first jobs. Drifting of the youth from rural areas to urban centers to work for non-existent jobs has accentuated the rate of urban unemployment and underemployment. Nigeria's unemployment rate according to Akande (2014) is growing at a very

fast pace Joseph (2015) observed that Nigeria's has one of the highest rates of youth employment in the world of about 60% The unemployed mostly encompass young adults who have graduated from tertiary educational institutions. Duru (2017) indicated that every year, about 3.8million young people who have dropped out of tertiary institution or have not received any higher education beyond secondary school flood the already over saturated labor market

In order to mitigate the pace of unemployment in Nigeria, the Federal Government of Nigeria(FGN, 2014), in the National Policy on Education (NPE) gave recognition to incorporating vocational education into the curriculum of schools to equip students with life-long entrepreneurial skills and knowledge relating to occupation in various sectors of economic and social life. Vocational education is understood to be a He long means of preparing students to acquire employable skills for occupational fields and for effective participation in the world of wood, The aim was to make students economically self-reliant in setting up their own businesses and becoming employers of others. Thus in an attempt to facilitate entrepreneurial development in the country, the government of Nigeria through various agencies and academic Institutions focused on development of models of entrepreneurial education and skills acquisition (Abubakar, 2020),

Entrepreneurship is the process through which an entrepreneur seeks innovation and employment. In other words, entrepreneurship can be described as creativity and innovation in the business arena. It was envisaged that on completing vocational education programmed, graduates would secure employment with the employable skills acquired or set up their own businesses as job creators to employ others.

Entrepreneurial development in educational institutions was seen as a panaceu for increased employment opportunities in an economy, as a function of education of the educational enterprises (Bonabo & Ndiomu, 2021).

This study therefore sought to access the influence of vocational education on acquisition of entrepreneurial skills for self-employment or paid-employment.

Statement of the Problems

Presently, there is a huge challenge of increase in unemployment in the country. There is need for creation of jobs and also acquisition of skills by the youth to be useful to themselves and their communities in order to reduce the rate of unemployment in the society. Employers of labor lament of graduates not possessing the needed competencies to be employable in the labor market. This may be as a result of graduates not having employable skills. Many graduates are moving around the streets of major cities in search for white-collar jobs which are not available Acquisition of entrepreneurial skills would make graduates job creators and not job seekers, to mitigate the unemployment situation in the country. Introduction of entrepreneurial education into tertiary instigations was meant for graduates to acquire technical skills and to become self-employed with business creation capacities acquired through entrepreneurial education It was against this background that this study examined the influence of entrepreneurship skills acquisition on employability among entrepreneurship education students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to examine the effect of entrepreneurship skills acquisition on employability among entrepreneurship education students in Usmanu University, Sokoto. Specifically the study sought to:

1. Determine the extent to which technical skills acquired has enhanced employability potentials of entrepreneurship education students in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto.
2. Determine the extent to which communication skills acquired has influenced employability potentials of entrepreneurship education students employability in Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto.

Research Questions

In pursuance of the objectives, the following research questions were raised to guide the study.

- 2 To what extent has technical skills acquisition of entrepreneurship education students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto enhanced their employability potentials?

- 3 To what extent has communication skills acquisition influenced employability potentials of entrepreneurship education students in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto?

METHODOLOGY

The study used a survey research design aimed at determining the effect of entrepreneurship education on acquisition of employable skills and competencies among students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto. It was a cross sectional study to establish the relationship between entrepreneurship education and acquisition of employable skills and competencies, the population comprised all undergraduate students of entrepreneurship education numbering 300 and all lecturers numbering (30 of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto. According to Alamu and Olukosi (2010), the major concern in a research is an unbiased sample. The study therefore used pure random sampling technique to select 30 students running entrepreneurship education and 15 lecturers of different subjects in the department to ensure that every member of the population had equal probability of being included in the sample thereby ensuring an unbiased representation of the population. The sample size was 45 in total. The instrument for the study was a researcher-designed questionnaire titled: Effect of Entrepreneurship Education on Acquisition of Employable Skills and competencies. Assessment Questionnaire (IEEAESAQ). The instrument for the study was fashioned after a four-point likert rating on dimensions of agreement and disagreement of respondents. The respondents were required to express their opinions in terms of strong agreement (SA), Mere Agreement (MA), Mere Disagreement (MD) and Strong Disagreement (SD).

Reliability of the instrument was ensured through a pilot test administered to 20 students and 5 lecturers from Faculty of Education Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto. Data collected through this dummy trial were analyzed using split-half reliability method which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.78 indicating that the instrument was good for eliciting data for the study. Data elicited by the study were analyzed by frequency counts and weighted means. Weights were assigned to response options thus

- 4 for Strong Agreement (SA)
- 3 for Mere Agreement (MA)
- 2 for Mere Disagreement (MD)
- 1 for Strong Disagreement (SD)

Based on the weights, weighted means were computed for each response variable and the resultant index used to decide agreement or otherwise among respondents regarding the propositions in the response variables.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

In these analyses, the critical mean score adjudged to decide agreement or disagreement is 2.50. Based on this definition, every preposition of employability potentials with a mean score of more than 2.50 is adjudged to be agreement among respondents to the preposition. On the contrary, for any preposition of employability potentials for which a less than 2.50 is observed is adjudged to denote disagreement among respondents to the preposition.

Research question one sought to examine the extent to which technical skills acquisition in entrepreneurship education of students of Shehu Shagari University of Education has enhanced employability potentials and the results presented in table 1.

Table 1: Responses as Regards Technical Skills Acquisition in Entrepreneurship Education Enhancing Employability Potentials of Students in Shehu Shagari University of Education

Employability Potentials	SA	MA	MD	SD	Mean	Decision
Ability to write business plan	15	12	8	10	2.71	Agreed
.Keeping of confidential documents through data processing	14	15	6	10	2.73	Agreed
Understanding the social economic and political framework of the business environment	23	12	5	5	3.18	Agreed
Having a change of attitude from being a job-seeker to a job provider	20	12	7	6	3.02	Agreed

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 1 detail respondents' views on technical skills acquisition of entrepreneurship education and how it has enhanced employability potentials of students. As regards ability to write business plan as employability potential, respondents were generally in agreement as evidenced by a mean score of 2.71 which is greater than the critical mean score of 2.50 As regards keeping of confidential documents secret through data processing as an aspect of employability potentials, the observed mean score was 2.73 which indicates respondents agreement to the assertion as it is greater than the critical mean score of 2.50. With reference to understanding the social, economic and political framework of the business environment, respondents were generally in agreement as evidenced by a mean score of 3.18 which is greater than the critical mean score of 2.50. As regards having a change of attitude from being a job seeker to a job provider respondents were generally agreed as it indicated a mean score of 3.02 which is greater than the critical mean score of 2.50.

In general, the respondents agreed that acquisition of technical skills has enhanced employability potentials of students to make them employable on graduation.

Research question two sought to examine to what extent communication skills acquisition has influenced employability potentials among students of entrepreneurship education in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto and the results presented in table 2.

Table 2: Responses as Regards Communication Skills Acquisition Influencing Employability Potentials of Entrepreneurship Education Students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto

Employability Potentials	SA	MA	MD	SD	Mean	Decision
Innovative skills	15	20	5	5	3.00	Agreed
Social skills	10	5	15	15	2.22	Disagreed
Leadership skills	20	10	5	10	2.89	Agreed
Motivational skills	16	15	9	5	2.93	Agreed

Source: Field Survey, 2025

As regards innovative skills influencing employability potentials of entrepreneurship education students, the mean score observed was 3.00 which is greater than the critical mean score of 2.50. This presupposes that respondents were generally agreed on innovative skills enhancing employability potentials of students. With regard to social skills impacting employability potentials of students, the mean score of the responses was observed to be 2.22 which is less than the critical mean score of 2.50 This indicates that respondents were in disagreement that social skill positively Impact employability potentials of students. With regard to leadership skills enhancing employability potentials of entrepreneurship education students, the mean score of the responses was observed to be 2.89 which is greater than the critical mean score of 2.50 This shows that respondents were in agreement that leaderships skills improve employability potentials of students. As regards motivational skill enhancing employability potentials of students the mean score of the responses was observed to be 2.73 which is greater than the critical mean score of 2.50. This indicates that respondents were in agreement that motivational skills improve entrepreneurial skills of students and hence their employability potentials. In general respondents were in agreement that acquisition of communication skills enhances employability potentials of students and hence making them employable either in the formal or informal sectors of the economy on graduation.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study has revealed that acquisition of technical skills in entrepreneurship education enhances employability potentials of students. This is evidenced by the that having a change of attitude from being a job seeker to being a job provider, ability to write a business plan, keeping of confidential documents secret through data processing and understanding the socioeconomic and political framework of the business environment have been shown to influence acquisition of employable skills among businesses education students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto. This finding is in line with Ojo, et al. (2022) who opined that entrepreneurship education plays an important role in equipping trainees with requisite technical skills that combine to make a

graduate of entrepreneurial education a provider of jobs rather than being a job-seeker, the study also indicated that acquisition of communication skills enhances employability potential of students on graduation. Effective communications in the workplace among co-workers promote understanding and cohesion if there should be progress. Leadership skills, motivational skills and innovative skills as components of communication skills ensure team spirit in the workplace and achievement of objectives. This is corroborated by Azih and Wagbara (2018) who reported that communication skills acquisition is a very necessary condition to acquire and maintain positions in employment environments.

CONCLUSION

The study established that acquisition of technical skills has positively influenced the chances of gaining employment on graduation. Acquisition of appropriate skills in communication ensures team spirit and understanding among co-workers and therefore enhances the probability of securing employment when one is proficient in communicating.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made

1. Teachers/lecturers entrepreneurship education are enjoined to encourage students to put into practice the knowledge acquired during their studentship by starting, operating and running of their own business ventures in order to be self-reliant and independent of other for sustenance
2. Students are encouraged to pursue further training and acquisition of skills even after graduation from college to further develop their skills and competencies in a rapidly-changing employment landscape so as to be continuously relevant in the world of work.

REFERENCES

- Abubakar S. G. (2020). Refocusing Education System Towards Entrepreneurship Development in Nigeria: A Tool for Poverty Eradication *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 15(11), 140-150
- Akande, T. (2014). Nigeria's Unemployment Rate Growing at a Very Fast Pace: *Journal of Economic Development*, 45(2), 75-89.
- Adamu O.J & Olukosi Y.A. (2010). Methodology Approach in Educational Research *Journal of Educational Research* 12(13),45-56
- Azih, N & Wagbara. S.O. (2018) Leveraging on Modern Instructional Delivery Strategies for Development of Employability Skills of Business Education Students. *Nigeria Journal of Business Education*. 3(1),1-10
- Banabo, E & Ndiomu K. (2021) Entrepreneurial Education: Strategy for Sustainable Development *Asian Journal of Business Management*, 3(3)192-202.
- Duru, P. (2017). Labor Market Saturation: The Challenges of Youth Unemployment in Nigeria. *International Journal of Social and Economic Studies*, 12(3), 22-35.
- Federal Government of Nigeria. (2014). National Policy on Education. Federal Ministry of Information
- Joseph, A. (2015). Youth Unemployment in Nigeria: A Critical Review, *Journal of African Studies*, 10(1), 48-62.
- National Bureau of Statistics. (2024). Labor Force Statistics: Unemployment and Underemployment Report. *Daily Trust*.
- Ojo, M.O., Akinola, O.T. & Gotip. N.W. (2022). Assessing the Importance of Education in Entrepreneurship Development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Development*, 11(2),169-174.